

TEXTBOOK EVALUATION

AN ANALYSIS OF LISTENING IN Q2: SKILLS FOR SUCCESS LISTENING AND SPEAKING FOR ENGLISH-MAJOR FRESHMEN AT HUFU

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ABSTRACT

Choosing a book which is suitable for all students' levels is a challenge. After a long time searching for books, our faculty decided to choose the textbook Q2: Skills for success Listening and Speaking. However, we recognize that the repeated listening tasks from the book easily make learners feel bored and have no motivation in learning listening. Therefore, this paper attempts to evaluate the presentation and the effectiveness of listening skill in Q2: Skills for success Listening and Speaking textbook (Snow & Zwier, 2011) for first –year students of English major at Ho Chi Minh University of Food Industry. The textbooks were evaluated by using evaluation criteria and textbook evaluation checklist by Cunningsworth (1995). The purpose of this study is to find out the good points and limitations of textbook, since then evaluate the effectiveness of the textbook and make appropriate judgment if necessary.

Key words: textbook evaluation, evaluation criteria listening, good points, limitations

1 INTRODUCTION

In ESL classroom, materials play an important part. Graves (2000) said that the textbook is used as a standard source of information for formal study of a subject and as an instrument for teaching and learning. For students it provides security, and for teachers it provides syllabus for the course and a basis for assessing. Moreover, a textbook provides a set of activities, visual aids to save teacher time in finding and developing materials. For this reason, choosing a good and appropriate textbook for most students is a very important decision that must be made. Besides the textbook, a learner is a key factor contributing to the success of the lesson. Although the textbook is well organized, is good on pictures and presentation, the low background knowledge of learners on vocabulary, grammar, skills might lead the learning and teaching to become meaningless. At HUFU, the majority of students come from different parts of Vietnam, so their English levels are not the same in one class. Some can understand and follow the directions from the book and teacher, but some can't. As a result, choosing a textbook becomes a crucial issue.

Q2: Skills for success Listening and Speaking is used as the main textbook for first-year English-major course at HUFU English-major course. As the title of the textbook said, there is a combination of listening and speaking skill in each unit. However, this paper just mentions the

Listening skill. The textbook contains 10 units. Each unit in the textbook includes two listening texts which are called listening 1 and listening 2. Listening 1 is a long conversation but listening 2 is usually a monologue. Before listening, students go through the warm –up, vocabulary preview, then listen for main ideas and listen for details in each lesson of listening. After each listening lesson there are group discussion questions.

At HUFU the textbook Q2: Skills for success Listening and Speaking (Snow & Zwier, 2011) is being conducted to first year students majoring in English and this has been the third year since this textbook was used. There has been a lot of researcher mentioning the textbook evaluation so far; however, evaluating the textbook strengths and limitations to fit students in HUFU has never been made before.

Therefore, the purpose of this paper is that the author to focuses on evaluating its listening part through 3 years teaching and learning to find out what are the strengths and weaknesses in listening section of the current textbook. The evaluation results can enhance the effectiveness of using the textbook by helping teachers to understand what areas of the textbook need or to what extent adaptation of other new teaching materials is necessary.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Role of Textbook

In today's classrooms, textbooks serve as tool and tutor and guidebook. Teachers throughout the world use texts to guide their instruction, so textbooks greatly influence on how content is delivered. Besides learner factors, a textbook is an indispensable tool for teaching and learning. It plays an extremely crucial part contributing to the success for second language learning. As Graves (2000) said, a textbook is regarded as one of the many sources that teachers can make a reference to create interesting and effective lessons and as a framework of guidance and orientation. In case of shortage of teachers, textbook plays a role as a substitute and helps the classroom in order. The way each chapter is designed and structured can be a direction of how would the lesson be conducted (Hutchinson & Torres 1994). A textbook provides students with security because they have a kind of a road map of the course and they know what to expect and what is expected from them. A good textbook should provide users with necessary skills and activities for language practice and interaction. O'Neill (1982), for example, argued that "Since language is an instrument for generating what people need and want to say spontaneously, a great deal must depend on spontaneous, creative interaction in the classroom." If the interaction does not occur, what the book brings to users is meaningless and invalid. Lee (1997) found that textbooks can also serve as a tool to motivate and stimulate learning a language. The learning environment in which learners are motivated and feel happy and positive may increase the language acquisition, then making language learning more effective. Moreover, Crawford (2002) presented that a textbook must be a useful resource which supplies up-to-date information for learners. A textbook will be effective if it contains the following: authentic and relevant contents, clear and culturally sensitive visuals and graphics, and various learning styles. Also, it can provide useful inputs for learners to learn English language effectively. That means,

comprehensive evaluation can investigate the actual usefulness and effectiveness of the inputs in the English language textbook and its accompanying materials. Ellis (1997) said that a good material should have useful information and potential values in relation with learners' objectives. On the other hand, any textbooks must be used wisely by teachers because not all information presented in the textbook fits all the classrooms in the same way. Some research showed that it is extremely common to see ESL lecturers and professionals with textbooks in classrooms and that they can be indispensable in some stage of their career (Byrd, 2001). To make the most effective use of a textbook, however, teachers must decide which textbooks are appropriate for their needs. A teacher needs to determine the extent to which a textbook focuses on and is aligned with a coherent set of significant, age-appropriate student learning goals.

As a result of these, selecting a proper textbook for a class is an important task which must be done.

2.2 The Needs for Textbook Evaluation

Nowadays, there is a variety of textbooks on the markets that can make book choice become easier. However, choosing a textbook should be taken into account and need evaluating because this can have a great impact on teaching and learning process. The evaluation should be conducted continuously to ensure if the quality of the textbook fits the language teaching and learning. Green (1926) & Mukundan (2007) argued that the quality of a textbook is so important that it can determine the success or failure of a course. There are two other reasons for textbook evaluation: evaluate the intention to adopt new course books and evaluate its points of strengths and weaknesses. There is no perfect book. Hence, the purpose of textbook evaluation is to find out weakness and strength existing in that textbook (Cunningsworth, 1995). Mukundan (2009) also pointed two purposes of evaluation. The first is to select the textbook and the second is to determine the effectiveness of the textbook while they are used. According to Ellis (1997), textbook evaluation helps teachers evaluate the effectiveness of the textbook, the level of learners' interest in the book, and then make appropriate judgment to fit learners' acquisition. Another reason of Tomlinson (2003) suggested that although textbooks written by experts and professionals are excellent at quality of organization and design, they tend to be short of quality of creativeness and imagination. Cunningsworth (1995) stated that textbook evaluation helps teachers to acquire useful, accurate, systematic, and contextual insights into the overall nature of textbook material.

As a result of these, textbook evaluation is a task should be taken into account and be conducted regularly to make in-time adjudgement.

2.3 Textbook Evaluation

So far, there have been many arguments on textbook evaluating. According to Cunningsworth (1995) and McGrath (2002), the first normal process to evaluate a textbook is the impression it makes on people. He presented that by looking quickly through a textbook from its cover to some chapters, we can evaluate the textbook overview of its impression, design, structure, sequence and quality. In general, if these issues meet the first requirement called impression, the textbook

will be looked closely to enter the next step called in-depth evaluation. Vice versa, if they don't draw attention or aren't impressive at the first look, this textbook might be screened out of the evaluation of choosing a textbook.

A process of evaluation, according to Cunningsworth (1995), there are three stages including pre-use, in-use and post-use. Tomlinson (2003) explained pre-use evaluation can facilitate the textbook selection process by gaining an impression. It makes prediction about potential value of materials on people using them. This type of evaluation is often subjective, so it's not always reliable because teachers scan a book quickly to gain an impression about its values. Pre-use focuses on quickly analyzing these kinds of information of the book: objective, level, skills, activities, topics, length and organization of units, target learners. However, this stage is very important as it establishes potential suitability of a textbook. In-use evaluation can help examine the suitability of the textbook while using them. In-use evaluation is more reliable than pre-use evaluation because it can measure the effect of materials whilst using them rather than just predicting. As Ellis (1997) said, whilst-use stage "determine whether it is worthwhile using the materials again, which activities work and which do not, and how to modify the materials to make them more effective for future use." Lastly, post-use evaluation can help to assess the actual validity of the textbook on the users and in future use in terms of short-term effects such as motivation, instant learning, learner's achievability and long-term effect such as durable learning and application. This type of evaluation is useful for identifying the strengths and weaknesses during the using of textbook (Urb, 1996).

3 EVALUATION METHOD

According to Cunningsworth (1995), the creation of extensive evaluation checklists by leading experts provides criteria for detailed coursebook analysis. Cunningsworth's checklist for evaluation and selection covers criteria such as "aims", "design", "language content", "skills", and "methodology", as well as "practical considerations such as cost and obtainability."

Therefore, the author as a lecturer with three years working with this textbook uses Cunningsworth's checklist evaluation method via closed questions as a background to analyze evaluation process and find out the strengths and weaknesses of listening parts of the textbook.

4 FINDINGS

Each unit in the textbook includes two listening texts which are called listening 1 and listening 2. Listening 1 is a long conversation but listening 2 is usually a monologue. Before listening, students go through the warm-up, vocabulary preview, then listen for main ideas and listen for details in each lesson of listening. After each listening lesson there are group discussion questions.

In general, the textbook meets the criteria of evaluation process including pre-use evaluation, in-use evaluation and post-use evaluation because it makes quick impressions on teachers and learners in term of beautiful cover and illustrated photos, meaningful and practical contents, appropriate activities with level and target of learners. The layout is very professionally presented

and creates an impressive overview. This main format of the textbook is listening for main idea and details; therefore, it lessens students' unfamiliarity, and after covering a couple of units, students can know what to be expected. This helps save teacher's and students' time. Also, the speaking speed is medium fast and clear which helps students can catch up with the listening for detail task. At the beginning of each lesson, there are some pictures and questions raised to warm up and to draw learners' attention. Vocabulary is very helpful in helping learners easily catch up and understand each listening text. These are strengths of the textbook.

However, some limitations of the textbook have arisen. The activities of listening for main ideas and for details are just around of true, false statements, choosing the correct answers, matching and answering the questions which, on the one hand, help learners to be familiar with the structure and improve listening skill; on the other hand, easily make learners feel bored and feel nothing new and challenging. Moreover, although the content in general is interesting, it is always a too long conversation or monologue. As a result, learners usually have difficulty in listening for main idea. Also, the speaking speed in the listening is medium which is easy for listeners to understand but it can make students fall asleep and be distracted. The textbook has recorded material like CDs whose sound is very clear but there are no video materials.

5 CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on findings and discussions, it can be concluded that regarding the presentation of listening skill, the textbook was relevant to the evaluation criteria proposed by Cunningsworth (1995) though no video materials might be a problem in making the listening more interesting. It might be a good idea for publishers to provide video sources as supporting materials.

Although there are many listening activities, these kinds of activities focus on listening for main ideas and details which sometimes cause difficulty for learners because any classes are made up with a variety of levels. Therefore, there should be various listening tasks from easy to difficult in order to suit most students' levels.

The results of this study make a variety of interesting suggestions and offer potential for further research. First, it would be interesting to evaluate other textbooks based on evaluation criteria by Cunningsworth (1995). Second, surveys, questionnaires, interviews that follow should be conducted to get feedback from teachers and students who have actually used Q2: Skills for success Listening and Speaking, and to have a full picture of the quality of the textbook. Although the paper has already showed some strengths and weaknesses of the textbook, they are not all. Therefore, the author hope there will be more evaluation research on this textbook to facilitate teaching and learning.

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APPENDIX

COURSEBOOK EVALUATION CHEKLIST		
	YES	NO
1. Are the contents of the textbook interesting and understandable?		
2. Is the content of the textbook challenging enough to boost new learning?		
3. Are the subject and contents motivating?		
4. Is the length of each listening task appropriate to learners' level?		
5. Is the layout and presentation clear?		
6. Are illustrated photographs and pictures integrated into the topic?		
7. Does the coursebook look interesting and fun?		
8. Is there a variety of listening tasks in each unit?		
9. Is the delivery speed of listening too slow?		
10. Is the delivery speed of listening too fast?		
11. Are there any video materials supporting listening?		
12. Are the contents meaningful and practical in real-life?		
13. Is the new vocabulary helpful in understanding listening tasks?		
14. Does the textbook contain potential values in each unit?		
15. Are learners encouraged to use the language creatively?		
16. Are there any activities helping learners expose their ideas.		
17. Are there activities for communicative interaction?		